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Research article

Dynamics of Internal Migration in the Southwest Region of Bangladesh

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Abstract: Bangladesh is well-known as a developing nation around the world. Migration is common in Bangladesh, particularly within the country. To raise their living conditions (income, housing, education, health, communication, etc.), many people move to new areas. Dacope Upazila is located in the southwestern region of Bangladesh, and this study seeks to examine the factors that contribute to the dynamics of internal migration by assessing the social and economic changes in the living standard of internal migrants following the migration. Both primary and secondary data were analysed statistically. The use of a questionnaire survey has allowed for the collection of primary data. Priority ranking matrix, Satisfaction Index, Economic Status Index (ESI), and Social Status Index (SSI) were computed to analyse the data. Statistical methods were also used to derive demographic information of the migrants. The study found that the majority of migrants were men who were either unemployed or living in poverty. The lack of economic opportunities, the inability to protect one's financial well-being from natural disasters, and the absence of adequate market infrastructure were the primary driving forces of migration. Migratory choices are heavily influenced by economic factors, and a lack of employment opportunities was ranked as the top factor. The Satisfaction Index highlighted the high levels of contentment experienced by internal migrants. Both the ESI and SSI showed greater improvement in the migrants' social and economic standing after migration. One could say that internal migration has a significant effect on the resulting population.

Keywords: Internal Migration; Priority Ranking Matrix; Satisfaction Index; Economic Status Index; Social Status Index

1. Introduction

Migrating within Bangladesh is becoming an increasingly popular option for the economically disadvantaged as a means of improving their standard of living. They are leaving their current location in search of better economic prospects elsewhere (Alam & Islam, 2014). Several factors, including those of a socioeconomic, demographic, and cultural nature (Ishtiaque & Rahman, 2007), are driving migration within Bangladesh. The loss of land, the need for a new job, the hope for higher wages, and the lessons learned from one's past all play a role in perpetuating income disparity (Ishtiaque & Mahmud, 2011). Most of these people are just passing through; most return within six months. More than two-thirds of coastal Bangladesh's permanent migrants are moving from the countryside to the city, a trend that has accelerated dramatically over the past three decades (BBS, 2011; Braun, 2019).

Afsar (2003) reports that between 1984 and 2010, the permanent rural-urban migration rate increased from 1.2 per thousand to 22.5. This has led to the growth of urban slums, where between 40 and 50 per cent of the population originates from rural areas and fleeing poverty (Ishtiaque & Ullah, 2019).

The “push forces” caused by climate change are already having an influence, even though economic and political causes continue to be the primary drivers of migration in today’s world. Many people may be displaced from their homes, either temporarily or permanently, as a direct result of global warming. Both developed and developing nations may be affected (Stern, 2006).

Kreft and Eckstein (2013) state that between the years 1993 and 2012, Bangladesh ranked high on the global climate risk index. The risk of natural disasters was used as a criterion for this ranking. As the first most vulnerable region to cyclones, it also ranks sixth most vulnerable to flooding due to the danger they pose to local populations. Both lists are ordered by the number of people who are likely to be impacted (Pelling et al., 2004). It is also the third most susceptible to flooding as sea levels rise (Pender, 2008). Bangladesh is divided into 64 districts, 19 of which are on the water. Further, Mallick (2011) found that 28% of Bangladesh’s entire population resides in coastal regions. Because of this, Bangladesh is among the top ten nations in the entire globe in terms of the percentage of its population that lives in coastal areas (Pender, 2008). Climate change is not a new phenomenon, and nor is the disruption and displacement of human populations that it causes. That human actions are the primary cause of both ecological vulnerabilities and global warming has been proven beyond a reasonable doubt (IPCC, 2007).

The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that contribute to the dynamics of internal migration in one of the coastal areas located in the Southwest region of Bangladesh. The identification of the demographic and social characteristics of the migrants, the assessment of the drivers of internal migration, and the evaluation of the social and economic changes in the living standard of internal migrants after the migration are the primary focuses of the study.

2. Significance of the Study

The process of migration can be viewed as socio-demographic in nature. People have been moving around from one location to another, either on purpose or by chance, ever since ancient times. According to Ma et al. (2011), sometimes they migrate due to natural causes and other times they migrate due to different causes triggered by humans. It’s possible for people to migrate either within the same sociopolitical area or to move away from the area altogether. Migration within a country has picked up steam in recent years. As a result, it is essential to have an understanding of the factors that motivate people to move from one location to another as well as the processes involved in migration. In addition to this, it is essential to have an understanding of the socio-economic and impoverishment status of migrants, which can be understood as an indicator of the migrants’ level of contentment after departing from their country of origin. Any kind of economic development initiative can be carried out in an effective manner if done so through this.

People who live in coastal rural areas often leave their homes and move away from their communities in order to improve their socioeconomic circumstances. It is essential to determine the push factors that are causing people to migrate, as well as the problems that are serving as the primary drivers of internal migration. After migrating, they involve themselves in a variety of activities in the destination place that generate income for them. Given the motivation behind their move here, is it possible for them to accomplish what they set out to do? They want to improve their socioeconomic condition; will this allow them to improve their socioeconomic status? Is it possible for them to lessen their level of poverty overall? As a result, carrying out research on the socioeconomic situation of migrants and anything else that pertains to them is not only necessary but also the most logical course of action to take.

Impoverishment is a societal curse in Bangladesh because it is a developing nation. It’s a crucial part of progress in the context of migration. In order to better their economic situation and escape poverty, many people move from rural areas to urban centres or from one region to another (Siddique, 2003). As a result, poverty reduction is a primary motivation for migration. Therefore, research into how migration affects people’s ability to make ends meet is essential. Again, migration has become a way to make ends meet, and it has long been recognised as crucial to the economic and social advancement of the poor. Therefore, the government can take appropriate policy towards internal migration in order to alleviate poverty if its effects on poverty can be investigated. This research is thus extremely important.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Migration and Internal Migration

All forms of human movement are included under the umbrella term “migration” (Haider, 2010). When people migrate, they leave their home country and settle in a new one, either permanently or temporarily. It includes any kind of human migration, whether permanent or temporary. Internal migration takes place within a country, while international migration takes place between countries. People migrate from one area to another in search of better economic opportunities or to start a new life. Mahmood (1996) defines migration as the temporary and intentional movement of a population to a foreign country. Meyer along with Clyed (1970) defined mobility separately from migration. They distinguish between mobility (travelling within established boundaries) and migration (travelling to new areas). These limits may be physical, organisational, cultural, or racial (Haider, 2010). A permanent change in one’s place of residence constitutes migration, as defined by Beijeer (1969). According to Saint and William, migration is a societal phenomenon influenced by shifts in the economic and social order. According to Haider’s (2010) research, migration is the intentional movement of people to areas of the country with a high concentration of industries and job opportunities. Various forms of migration are visible in any given society. This includes: 1) domestic (rural-urban, rural-rural, urban-rural, and urban-urban). 2) Cross-border (involving travel between different countries). Both can be arbitrary and coercive in nature.

3.2. Factors of Migration

Humans migrate for a variety of reasons, including those that affect their economy, population, culture, politics, and the environment. The causes of migration can be broken down into two categories: push factors and pull factors. To move from one’s home country to another, one must first consider the push factors (Kainth, 2009). For instance, the dearth of job openings, the prevalence of unemployment and underdevelopment, the state of the economy, the exhaustion of natural resources, and the prevalence of natural disasters. However, pull factors are those that entice migrants to a particular region (area of destination), such as the availability of jobs and better educational opportunities (Haider, 2010, Kainth, 2009, Farhana et al., 2012, Afsar 2003, Rokib, 2009). Bangladeshi internal migration seems to be caused by a combination of economic and environmental factors (Haider, 2010) as well as social and cultural ones (marriage, familial disputes, societal prejudice, social issues, chaos in politics, overpowering village elders, greater job prospects, higher standards of living, more educational opportunities, etc.). Better living conditions are a result of better job opportunities, better educational and health care facilities, and other social amenities, as mentioned by Haider.

3.3. Migration and Change in Socio- Economic Condition

Migration is a multifaceted process that can have material or immaterial motivations and take place across a wide range of temporal and spatial contexts. In the eyes of economic theorists, migrants are free agents seeking better economic opportunities elsewhere. In their working paper, H. Waddington and R. Sabates-Wheeler investigate the ties between economic hardship and relocation. In particular, they look into how poverty and precarity influence people’s decisions to leave their homes. In response to economic development, De Haan (2002) investigated how migration often represents a last resort for the poor. According to De Haan along with Rogaly (2002), migration is a viable option for maintaining one’s standard of living over time. It happens when people are confronted with a crisis on multiple fronts, including the physical, economic, social, and political. The poor are especially vulnerable to food insecurity, according to research by Ellis (1998). The poor are more likely to be forced to migrate as a result of their vulnerability. An overview of migration and poverty reduction in Moldova was provided by Pantiru, Black, and Sabates-Wheeler (2007) in their working paper. They drew on a survey of relevant literature and interviews with officials in Chisinau. According to their research, the number of people leaving Moldova for other countries is still rising significantly. It caused large amounts of money to be sent back home, which helped boost domestic demand and had a beneficial effect on fighting poverty and starting new businesses (Islam, 2007).

In numerous regions of the developing world, migration is the primary means by which the rural poor diversify their income and ensure their survival. Because females can send greater amounts of money than sons can, women make up the majority of migrants in countries like the Philippines and

Latin America (Lauby & Stark, 1988). Outmigration is the primary driver of economic growth and improvement in many low-income regions of Bangladesh, according to research by Haider (2010). De Haan et al. (2000) looked at two different areas of Bangladesh and found that migrant households were less likely to be landless and owned more land on average than those without migrants. In their study, Farhana et al. (2012) investigate what causes internal migration. Economic and social factors, such as poverty, joblessness, political and ethnic conflict, religion, etc., were found to be the primary drivers of migration through a combination of survey, observation, and case study methods.

They also discovered that when migration occurs, poverty and unemployment are the driving forces behind the poor villagers leaving their homes for the cities. Most people who moved to the city were able to significantly better their standard of living as a result. That is, they discovered that migration helped the poor of Bangladesh by reducing their level of poverty. Although migration is a key component of many low-income people's strategies for survival in the developing world, it may not be an option for the most impoverished of the poor. Migration is a last resort for low-income and vulnerable households, as its benefits depend on the household's initial level of destitution rather than on whether it represents an attractive alternative livelihood. According to Zug (2006), it is common for grocery store staple prices to rise during Monga. People in rural areas have to move to the cities of Rajshahi, Chittagong, Dhaka, Barisal, Sylhet, etc. in order to survive.

Based on the reviewed literature, it is clear that migration can be understood in a variety of ways, that many different factors contribute to migration, and that migration itself helps to improve the lives of the poor. However, the vast majority of published works have only focused on the migrant's financial situation or family-related factors. As a result, the economic and social standing of migrants is affected by internal migration, particularly from rural to urban areas. As a result, there is a lack of information regarding the relationship between internal movement and contentment with one's means of subsistence as well as one's socioeconomic and poverty levels. Once again, most studies used a variety of statistical methods to examine the factors influencing the internal migration of respondents. This research, however, uses an economic and social index as well as a satisfaction index to measure the well-being of internal migrants and their families.

4. Materials and Method

4.1. Research Area Selection

Khulna is the administrative centre of Khulna district as well as Khulna division, and the third-largest city in Bangladesh. The 991.57 sq. km. that make up Dacope Upazila (Khulna District) can be found between the coordinates of 22°24' and 22°40' north latitude and 89°24' and 89°35' east longitude. The area of Dacope Upazila along the southwestern coast of the country has been chosen as the research site. Dacope upazila is home to 15 2,316 people as of 2011 (according to the BBS). The upazila is divided into nine different unions. Due to its coastal location, the upazila has been severely impacted by cyclones in recent years (Kumar et al., 2010). A total of 250,000 people were impacted by the 2009 super cyclone Aila, and 9,000 were forced to relocate from their homes in Dacope upazila alone (USS, 2009).

Study Area Map of Dacope Upazila, Khulna, Bangladesh

Figure 1: Map of Dacope Upazila.

4.2. Population and Sample of Research

The population of the research is the total population of the nine unions of Dacope upazila. The sample size for the research has been fixed as 378 using the “Yamane formula” with a 95% confidence level, 10% precision, and 50% prevalence. The sample of the research has been equally distributed among the nine unions of the upazila. 42 samples have been chosen from each union.

4.3. Research Design and Data Collection Technique

The research has followed a mixed approach. Both primary data and secondary data have been used for the analysis. A semi structured questionnaire survey has been used for the research. To identify the migrants from the sample size, household survey has been used and to identify socio-economic changes in migrant’s livelihood both household survey and telephone survey have been used. So, in the research there are two groups of respondents. The household members are in one group and the migrants from the households are in another. The households in which single migrants have been found that means household

head migrated from his origin and the other members of the households remained in origin place are considered as migrant households.

4.4. Data Analysis Techniques

To collect quantitative data, semi-structured questionnaires have been designed for household and telephone survey. So, the research instruments of this study are questionnaires. SPSS and several statistical tools have been used to analyze the data. The basic framework for data collection is show in figure 02. Statistical techniques such as priority ranking, satisfaction index, economic status index and social status index have been used according to the following formula to analyze the collected data in the research.

Prepared by: Author, 2022

Figure 02: Framework for data analysis

4.3.1. Problem Priority Ranking

Priority Ranking Technique has been used to identify and rank the different problems in Dacope upazila. Mini scores have been calculated for each issue, with the lower the ranking value, the higher the priority score. (Miah and Weber, 1990).

$$\text{Total Priority Score} = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where, X_i = Score given to each problem by the individual respondent.

N = Total number of Respondent.

4.3.2. Satisfaction Index

An individual's level of contentment with various facets of life is measured using a satisfaction index. When the satisfaction index is measured from 0 to 1, 1 indicates extreme satisfaction, -1 extreme dissatisfaction, and 0 indicates neither extreme satisfaction nor extreme dissatisfaction. One definition of a satisfaction index can be found in Yea and Lee (1975) and Weber (1990), and it reads as follows:

$$I_s = (f_s - f_d) / N \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where,

I_s = Satisfaction Index

f_s = Number of satisfied respondents

f_d = Number of dissatisfied respondents

N = Total Number of respondents

4.3.3. Economic Status Index

The economic status index of respondents is a cutting-edge method of quantifying qualitative shifts (Islam et al., 2008). The sum of the shifts in specific economic indicators is used to produce this index. The formula for determining the Economic Status Index is:

$$ESI = \sum w_i \times f_i \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where,

w_i = Weight of the change in economic indicators

f_i = Number of respondents detecting the change

m = Magnitude that means the multiplication of the highest weight of change and total number of respondents

4.3.3. Social Status Index

To quantify qualitative shifts, the social status index of respondents is one method (Islam et al., 2008). The rate of change of particular social indicators is used to determine this index's value. The formula for determining social status is as follows:

$$SSI = \sum \frac{w_i \times f_i}{m} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where

w_i= Weight of the change in social indicators

f_i= Number of respondents detecting the change

m= Magnitude which means the multiplication of the highest weight of change and total number of respondents.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Demographic, Social, and Economic Characteristics of the Migrants

The residents of Dacope Upazila, Khulna, and their demographic and social characteristics are displayed in Table 01 below. There were more men than women who emigrated (80.90 percent versus 19.0 percent). That's indicative of the gender gap in migration, with males being more willing to leave their homes than females. Male and female migrants aged 15 and under made up 4.54 percent, while those aged 15-25 made up 32.73 percent. The 25-35 year old age group had the highest percentage of the population (48.02%). The percentages of those between the ages of 35 and 45, 45 to 55, and 55 and older were 9.09%, 3.63%, and 1.81%, respectively. It was discovered that the middle-aged were the most likely to have moved.

The marital status of the migrants is also displayed in Table 01. The percentage of single migrants is significantly higher than the percentage of married migrants, which stands at 30%. According to the data, 51.9% of migrants have completed both SSC and HSC, while 8.18 % have not completed elementary school and 11.81% have completed only through eighth grade. Table 01 displays the percentage of migrants with Bachelor's, Honours, and Master's degrees.

Table 1. Demographic and Social Characteristics of Migrants in Dacope Upazila

Demographic and Social Characteristics	Migrants	
	Frequency	Percentage
Sex of Migrants		
Male	89	80.90
Female	21	19.09
Age of Migrants		
<15	5	4.54
15-25	36	32.73
25-35	53	48.2
35-45	10	9.09
45-55	4	3.63
>55	2	1.81
Marital Status of Migrants		
Married	33	30
Unmarried	77	70
Education Level of Migrants		
No education	9	8.18
Up to Class Eight	13	11.81
SSC & HSC	57	51.9
Degree	19	17.27
Honors	7	6.36
Masters	5	4.54

Source: Field Survey, 2022

In Table 2, we see the migrants' pre-migration economic characteristics. The average income per month was 9,220 tk. The majority of the migrants (31.82%) were jobless. The remaining percentages of migrants worked in agriculture (20.9%) or private sector jobs (3.63%). According to Table 02, before leaving their home countries, about 23.64 percent of migrants worked in transportation, 6.36 percent ran their own businesses, 9.09 percent were day labourers and 4.54 percent did not have formal employment.

Seventy percent of migrants left Dacope Upazila because they were unhappy with their jobs and/or income. As can be seen in Table 02, roughly 30% of migrants were content with their job and income situations prior to migration. It was discovered that 53.64 percent of migrants did not have a place of their own to live prior to leaving Dacope Upazila, while 46.36 percent of migrants did have a place of their own to live prior to leaving, but it was in poor condition.

Table 2. Economic Characteristics of Household Head (HH) of Migrants (Before Migration)

Economic Characteristics of HH	Migrants HH	
	Frequency	Percentage
Monthly Average Income (Taka)	9220	
Occupation of HH		
Unemployed	35	31.82
Agricultural Activities	23	20.9
Private Job	4	3.63
Business	7	6.36
Day Labour	10	9.09
Transport Work	26	23.64
Others	5	4.54
Job and Income Satisfaction of HH		
Not Satisfied	77	70
Satisfied	33	30
Types of House Ownership of HH		
Own	51	46.36
Rent	59	53.64

Source: Field Survey, 2022

5.2. Internal Migration: Push and Pull Factors

Among the six main push factors identified in this study, the lack of employment opportunities was a significant factor, with 36.36 percent of migrant households citing this as the primary reason for leaving the Dacope upazila. The inability to make ends meet as a result of natural disasters was the second leading cause of people leaving Dacope Upazila (23.64 percent). About 16.36% of migrants moved due to a lack of market facilities for business, making this the third push factor. 11.82 percent of migrants cited a lack of access to healthcare as a driving force behind their decision to leave Dacope Upazila. Finally, Table 03 reveals that 1.81 percent of respondents cited Inadequate educational facilities as a driving factor.

Table 3. Main Push Factors for Leaving Dacope

Push Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of Income Opportunities	40	36.36
Insufficient Education Facilities	2	1.81
Lack of health services	13	11.82
Poor Transport Facilities	10	9.1
Income barriers from natural hazard	26	23.64
Lack of Market Facilities for business	18	16.36
Others	1	0.9

Source: Field Survey, 2022

There were also six primary Push factors that influenced migrants' final destination choices. The primary motivating factor was the prospect of higher earnings in the new location (cited by 72.7% of migrants). The second allure was the promise of financial security in the new community, with 11.8 percent of migrants reporting that they were more secure there than in their home of Dacope Upazila. As for the third reason, 6.36 percent of migrants said the destination had better shopping or market facilities for business. Table 04 displays that 4.54 percent of the pull was attributable to improved health services, while the percentages attributable to improved education and other facilities were both 0.9 percent.

Table 4. Main Pull Factors of Migrants for Selecting Destination

Pull Factors	Frequency	Percentage
Better Income Opportunities	80	72.7
Better Education Facilities	1	0.9
Better Health Facilities	5	4.54
Better Transport Facilities	3	2.72
Protection for Income from Natural Hazards	13	11.8
Better shopping or market facilities for business	7	6.36
Others	1	0.9

Source: Field Survey, 2022

5.3. Priority Ranking of Different Problems in Dacope

Preliminary data analysis revealed seven categories of issues plaguing Dacope Upazila, Khulna: inadequate income opportunities, inadequate educational facilities, inadequate health services, inadequate transport facilities, income barriers resulting from natural hazards, and inadequate market facilities for business. The questionnaire has been set up to rank these issues. According to Table 05, the primary motivation for people to leave Dacope Upazila was the lack of economic opportunities. Dacope Upazila is a disaster-prone area that causes income barriers, ranking second on the list. The third issue was the dearth of commercial infrastructure; business owners in Dacope face fewer prospects as a result. Inadequate communication infrastructure was cited as the fourth issue facing the residents of Dacope Upazila. The lack of health services, inadequate educational facilities, and other factors all made the list. The result is shown in table 05 has been formed by using problem priority ranking method.

Table 5. Rank of Problems in Dacope Upazila Influencing Migration Decision

Problems in Dacope	Problem Score	Problem Rank
Lack of Income Opportunities	153	1
Insufficient Education Facilities	668	6
Lack of Health Services	454	4
Poor Transport Facilities	541	5
Income barriers from natural hazard	228	2
Lack of Market Facilities for business	334	3
Others	702	7

Source: Field Survey, 2022

5.4. Comparison between Migrant's Present Location and Place of Origin

In order to make a comparison between the present and the place where they originated from, the satisfaction index method was utilised. The overall satisfaction index came in at 0.32, which, according to the scale, indicates a level of satisfaction that is positive. The satisfaction index can range from -1, which indicates that a person is extremely dissatisfied, to +1, which indicates that they are extremely satisfied. A value of 0 indicates that the individual is neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. The satisfaction index was determined based on a total of thirteen criteria, which were as follows: the nature of the job, the level of income, the housing facilities, the education facilities, the health service facilities, the transport facilities, the marketing facilities, the relationship with the community, the safety and security facilities, the cultural activities, the recreation facilities, communication with the

family members in Dacope, and the utility facilities. The satisfaction index value that was measured was the highest for the Level of Income criterion, coming in at 0.836. Positive satisfaction index values were found for Job Nature, Housing Facilities, Education, Health Service, Transport Facilities, Marketing Facilities, Cultural Activities, and Recreation Facilities respectively. These values were 0.518, 0.236, 0.390, 0.872, 0.581, 0.4, 0.3, and 0.5. The criteria like Job Nature and Level of income are represented by the positive value of the satisfaction index. The destination location has superior housing facilities, educational facilities, health service facilities, transport facilities, marketing facilities, cultural activity facilities, and recreational activity facilities compared to the Dacope Upazila location. The dissatisfaction index scores for Relationship with Community, Safety and Security, Communication with the Family Members in Dacope, and Utility Facilities were -0.181, -0.109, -0.036, and -0.109 respectively. The overall value of 0.32 indicates that migrants are satisfied, which indicates that migrants are more satisfied with their lives in the destination place, both socially and economically, than they were in Dacope Upazila.

Table 6. Satisfaction Index of the Migrants Compared to Place of their Origin

Criteria in Place of Destination	Migrants N=110						Satisfaction Index $I_s = (f_s - f_d) / N$
	Better (f_b)		Same		Worse (f_d)		
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	
Job Nature	68	61.818	31	28.181	11	10	0.518
Level of Income	97	88.181	8	7.272	5	4.545	0.836
Housing Facilities	45	40.909	46	41.818	19	17.272	0.236
Education	45	40.909	63	57.272	2	1.818	0.390
Health Service	98	89.090	10	9.090	2	1.818	0.872
Transport Facilities	65	59.090	44	40	1	0.909	0.581
Marketing Facilities	60	54.545	34	30.909	16	14.545	0.4
Relationship with Community	26	23.636	38	34.545	46	41.818	-0.181
Safety and Security	24	21.818	50	45.454	36	32.727	-0.109
Cultural Activities	50	45.454	43	39.090	17	15.454	0.3
Recreation Facilities	71	64.545	23	20.909	16	14.545	0.5
Communication with the family members in Dacope	19	17.272	68	61.818	23	20.909	-0.036
Utility Facilities	24	21.818	50	45.454	36	32.727	-0.109
Total	53.230	48.391	39.076	35.524	17.692	16.083	0.32

Source: Field Survey, 2022

5.5. Economic Status Index of Migrant's Household

Respondents' economic status index is a cutting-edge technique for quantifying qualitative shifts (Islam et al., 2008). This index is based on the sum of five different economic indicators' movements. Migrants' resources include their income, expenses, savings, land holdings, and non-productive assets. The level of economic success can be traced directly by income. The level of poverty can be gauged, in part, by looking at a family's spending habits. Savings give strength to the households and increase their capacity of coping with crisis (Islam, 2007). Ownership of land is also an important indicators of livelihood.

The extent of changes is rated using a like system, where the score for no change is 0, the score for a little change is 1, the score for a medium change is 2, the score for a high change is 3, and the score for a very high change is 4. Only the change in one of the respondents' indicators is counted as being non-existent, while the change in both indicators is counted as being only slightly significant. Considered to be a high change if there is a shift in at least three of the respondents' indicators; considered to be a very high change if there is a shift in all of the respondents' indicators. Table 7 presents the degree to which these indicators have changed as a percentage of their previous values.

Table 7. Economic Status of the migrants

Economic Status	Weight	Number of Migrants	Percentage
No Change	0	5	4.54
Small Change	1	19	17.27
Moderate Change	2	65	59.09
High Change	3	16	14.54
Very High Change	4	5	4.54
Total		110	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

$$\text{Economic Status Index (ESI)} = \sum \frac{w_i f_i}{m} \times 100$$

$$\text{ESI} = \frac{(0 \times 5) + (1 \times 19) + (2 \times 65) + (3 \times 16) + (4 \times 5)}{110 \times 4} \times 100 = \frac{0 + 19 + 130 + 48 + 20}{440} \times 100 = \frac{217 \times 100}{440} = 49.32\%$$

According to the table that was just presented, 4.54 percent and 14.54 percent of respondents' economic status rise "very highly" and "high" respectively. A sizeable proportion, approximately 59.09 percent, have experienced "medium change" in their economic standing. To reiterate, approximately 17.27 percent of respondents have "little change" in their economic status, while only 4.54 percent of respondents have "no change" in their economic status. There is a value of 49.32 percent for the economic status index.

5.6. Social Status Index of Migrant's Household:

The social status index of migrants was determined by taking into account five different variables, including their healthcare aptitudes, patterns of occupation, the status of their housing, and the availability of water and sanitation facilities (Islam, 2007). Table 8 displays the different types of housing and the respondents' length of membership.

Table 8. Changes on Housing status of Migrants

Types of House of the Migrants	Before Migration		After Migration		Percentage Change
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Katcha	53	48.18	2	1.81	-46.37
Semi Pucca	12	10.9	41	37.27	26.37
Tin Shed	40	36.36	42	38.18	1.82
Pucca	5	4.54	25	22.72	18.18

Source: Field Survey, 2022

According to Table 8, there were four distinct styles of home. These included katchas, semi-puccas, tin sheds, and paccas. The results of the field survey show that the housing situation has improved significantly. After migrating, the percentage of semi-pacca who own their own homes rose from 10.9 to 37.27 percent. Tin-shed dwellings as a whole rose again, this time to 38.18 percent from 36.36 percent. However, the percentage of people living in katchas and mud houses has dropped dramatically, from 48.18 percent to 1.81 percent, suggesting a decrease of 46.37 percent due to internal migration.

In order to sustain life, water must be present. This is especially related to the general health of the respondents' families and neighbourhoods (Islam, 2008, p.78). After moving, nearly all respondents (96.3%) used water from tube wells for cooking and other household uses. Before the migration, however, that number was only 18.18 percent. While 81.82 percent relied on water from a pond, river, or other source for cooking as well as other purposes prior to migration, only 3.63% do so now (Table-9).

Table 9. Change in Source of water of the migrants

Sources of water	Before migration		After migration	
	Number of respondents	Percentage	Number of respondents	Percentage
Pond, river or others	90	81.82	4	3.63
Tube well	20	18.18	106	96.36

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The quality of a family’s sanitary facilities is a major factor in determining their social status. It demonstrates that after migration, approximately ninety percent use sanitary and pit latrines, whereas before migration, only 23.63 percent did so. Prior to migration, approximately 43% and 42% of people relied on either an open latrine or a katcha, which is a type of latrine that is constructed from local materials but is not a sanitary type. Having said that, it has been modified after the migration. Only 11 percent of residents in Dacope use katcha latrines, and there was not a single respondent whose family still uses open toilets after migration (Table-10).

Table 10. Change in Sanitation of the migrants

Types of toilet	Before migration		After Migration	
	Number of household	Percentage	Number of household	Percentage
Sanitary	7	6.36	46	41.82
Pit	19	17.27	53	48.18
Katcha	43	39.09	11	10
Open	41	37.27	0	0

Source: Field Survey, 2022

After the migration of income-generating member, the other members of the households of migrants in Dacope Upazila use better health facilities, and the migrants’ occupational efficiency of migrants has increased significantly. The alterations in social status are broken down into five categories, and each category carries a different weight value, which ranges from 0 to 4 according to its category. Table 11 provides insight into the respondents’ social status, as shown in:

Table 11. Social Status of Migrants

Social Status	Weight	Number of Migrants	Percentage
No Change	0	2	1.81
Small Change	1	22	20
Moderate Change	2	53	48.18
High Change	3	21	19.09
Very High Change	4	12	10.91
Total		110	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

$$\text{Social Status Index (SSI)} = \sum \frac{w_i f_i}{m} \times 100$$

$$\text{SSI} = \frac{(0 \times 2) + (1 \times 22) + (2 \times 53) + (3 \times 21) + (4 \times 12)}{110 \times 4} \times 100 = \frac{0 + 22 + 106 + 63 + 48}{440} \times 100 = \frac{239 \times 100}{440} = 54.32\%$$

The table mentioned above reveals that the value of the average of the weighted index is 54.32 percent. According to Table 10, the social status of migrants improves to “very high” levels by approximately 12 percent. Twenty-one percent of respondents are considered to have “high change” in their social status, forty-three percent of respondents are considered to have “medium change,” and approximately twenty-two percent have minor change.

6. Conclusion

In countries where a large proportion of the population lives below the poverty line, migration has become an important strategy. For better economic opportunities, many people move within their own country, particularly from rural to urban areas. The standard of living of people generally improves as a result of migration. The respondent did not have a particularly impressive socio-economic background. Most of them were young people who had recently lost their jobs and were looking for ways to make money despite the threat of natural disasters. They left Dacope Upazila because of these factors. With an index value of 0.32, migrant satisfaction is high. After leaving Dacope, people were content. More than a third of respondents report a significant improvement in their economic status, and this is reflected in the Economic Index (ESI) value of 49.32%. The average index value of the respondents' social status increased by 5.43 percent as a result of the improvement in the economic situation of the households. The social index took into account a person's healthcare knowledge, occupational preferences, housing conditions, and access to clean water and sanitary facilities as its variables. Extreme poverty is a major driving factor in human migration. It would be instructive to investigate people's motivations for emigrating and the factors that influence those decisions. Besides aiding in migration forecasting, the findings could also form the basis for social and economic planning in cities hosting large numbers of temporary dwellers.

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